

Repository Profile:

Repository and CRIS at the University of Porto

At the University of Porto ([U.Porto](#)) both repository and CRIS are being used as part of the local e-infrastructure.

The Institutional Repository

In 2007, one year after the adhesion of the Council of Rectors of Portuguese Universities to the terms of the Berlin Declaration for Open Access, U.Porto made available on the Web its [Open Repository](#). The reasons underlying the creation of this repository by the University are related to the acknowledgement that free access to scientific literature is advantageous and particularly important for the advancement of science and the increase of visibility and impact of scientific works produced by the academic community. The main objective was therefore to aggregate the University CC-BY license works in a single “portal”, allowing document and metadata retrieval from meta-repositories, both in Portugal and abroad. On December 2008, the U.Porto Open Repository became part of the newborn Portuguese Open Access Scientific Repository ([RCAAP](#)). Soon afterwards the U.Porto Open Repository was extended to include a [Thematic Repository](#) and a pilot [Data Repository](#).

- U.Porto Open Repository is the largest institutional repository on RCAAP, the Portuguese Open Access Scientific Repository, hosting 32.616 full text CC-BY works as of September 2014.
- SIGARRA-CRIS and U.Porto Open Repository are interoperable. When on the SIGARRA-CRIS the full text of a publication is registered and available on a CC BY basis both the corresponding metadata and the digital object are automatically transferred to the U.Porto Open Repository.

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The Open Repository collects, preserves and provides the intellectual production, in full text and open access, of the academic community of U.Porto. The access is open under the conditions of the Creative Commons public license.

The Thematic Repository stores, preserves and provides informational resources produced by U.Porto in definite areas or for specific audiences. The access may require authentication depending on the collections or the resources.

The Data Repository stores, preserves and shares datasets created by researchers of U.Porto.

The CRIS

In 1996, with the aim of enabling faster access and dissemination of scholar, scientific, technical and other info-resources, stimulating at the same time a stronger collaboration among members of the academic community as well as between them and colleagues and practitioners in other higher education and research institutions and industries, U.Porto released its information system on the Web. This system was developed in-house at the Engineering Faculty of U.Porto (FEUP) and until 2003 was used only by this faculty.

From 2003 onward it was extended to the other 13 faculties of U.Porto being nowadays used by the entire academic community of the University, about 32.000 students, 2.400 teaching and research staff and 1.600 non-teaching staff. The information system of U.Porto, called [SIGARRA](#), is an integrated campus wide information system, covering all the main areas of the University activity. Thus the U.Porto CRIS is a SIGARRA component.

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Open Access Policy

The Senate of U.Porto approved the Open Access Policy of the University in September 2008. This policy applies to the scientific production of the academic community, covering journal articles, proceedings, master and doctoral theses, reports and other publications, as well. The importance of this regulation was rather significant because it embodies the institutional support and commitment to the principles of open access to scientific literature. As the primary source of the scholarly research information is the SIGARRA-CRIS, the U.Porto Open Access Policy is not a mandate but strongly supports the accessibility of works on a CC BY basis and defines the responsibilities of the different stakeholders towards this objective.

Besides, an internal U.Porto regulation establishes that the annual assessment of the teaching staff is exclusively based on the information registered on SIGARRA. The information necessary for this assessment goes beyond R&D and as SIGARRA is a comprehensive IS the development of a support module for this assessment was rather facilitated. All the 14 faculties of U.Porto use SIGARRA for this process, even though with differences in the evaluation regulations.

The approach followed led to what we believe is a worthwhile solution. The U.Porto Open Access Repository has grown stably and consistently, being the larger open access repository in Portugal, although having solely full text CC BY works.

U.Porto Data Curation Project

CRIS-IR Interoperability

The SIGARRA-CRIS covers the main functionalities of a CRIS, namely R&D units, scientific publication's metadata, scientific publication's full text, projects, patents, dissertations and thesis, researcher's web pages, researcher's activities reports, researcher's CV and researcher's assessment. Depending on each faculty policy, the library, the researcher himself or the researcher with the help of the library is responsible for registering all his scholarly works on SIGARRA-CRIS.

At U.Porto the intellectual property policy says that the rights to published papers and books belong entirely to the authors, so the authors themselves must register on SIGARRA-CRIS the access permissions they allow for each of their works. Also M.Sc. and Ph.D. students must register the access permissions they allow for their final thesis documents on SIGARRA-CRIS. Recently the Portuguese Government Decree-Law 115/2013 of 7 August requires M.Sc. and Ph.D. works to be deposit on a repository harvested by RCAAP. When on the SIGARRA-CRIS the full text of a publication, including master and doctoral thesis, is registered and available on a CC BY basis both the corresponding metadata and the digital object are automatically transferred to the U.Porto Open Repository. With this approach the CC BY works are immediately published on the Web. If there is an embargo period the metadata of the respective work as well as the corresponding digital object are kept on SIGARRA-CRIS, keeping metadata publicly available there. The authors may therefore be contacted for requesting a copy of the work. When the embargo period finishes the metadata and the digital object are automatically transferred to the U.Porto Open Repository.